

Detection of Medicine Information with Optical Character Recognition Using Android

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Abstract— Generally, people don't understand medical terms but need medicines, in this situation OCR is helpful and solves the problem. Healthcare Management is one of the most vital and fastest expanding sectors in the world today. People demand more medicine to deal with stress and other illnesses as lifestyles change. As a result, a huge amount of money is spent on medicines. The resulting medical waste is also enormous. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the global medical waste rate (HCWGR) is 2.5 kg/bed/day. In India, this rate is 1.55 kg / bed / day. Most of this waste is the medicine we throw away because we don't have any data about them. This medical waste is growing day by day, endangering the planet. With Covid19, the economic situation is more serious than ever. People need to search for paths to save money to improve their financial situation. Our project describes the same issue. We developed an application that identifies medicines using Optical Character Recognition (OCR) in this project. The application will include information such as drug names, available illnesses, side effects, generics, prices, and simple tips.

Keywords— Object Detection, Scale-Invariant Feature Transform, Speeded-Up Robust Features

I. INTRODUCTION

OCR (optical character recognition) is the use of technology to distinguish printed or handwritten text characters inside digital images of physical documents, such as scanned paper documents. The basic process of OCR involves examining the text of a document and translating the characters into code that can be used for data processing. OCR is sometimes also referred to as text recognition.

The physical form of a document is processed using a scanner in the first step of OCR. OCR software turns the

document into a two-color, or black and white, version once all pages have been duplicated. The light and dark regions of the scanned-in picture or bitmap are identified as characters that need to be recognized, while the light areas are designated as background.

There are many different techniques for OCR programs, but usually, you need to target a block of letters, words, or text at a time. With the help of OCR, you can recognize text without language barriers.

The characters are then identified using one of two algorithms:

1. The pattern recognition: The OCR program provides samples of text in various fonts and formats and compares and recognizes characters in scanned documents.
2. Feature Recognition: The OCR program applies rules related to a specific letter or number features to recognize letters in scanned documents.

Features can include the number of angled lines, intersecting lines, or curves in the text for comparison. For example, the capital "A" can be stored as two diagonals that intersect the central horizon.

Once the character is identified, it is converted to ASCII code and can be used on a computer system for further operations. Users should correct basic errors, proofread and make sure complex layouts were handled properly before saving the document for future use. we can use OCR and text summaries to extract drug names and display information such as names, usages, and dosages. In application

We tried different approaches to OCR and examined the effectiveness of each approach. Generally, the accuracy of optical character recognition is about 80%. Text extraction is still an area of open research, and much work is being done in this area.

The following is how the paper is organized: section II is devoted to the literature review. The proposed methodology results, which are carried out in Android, are presented in Section III. The experimental results are covered in Section IV, and Section V summarizes the project's work in terms of conclusion and future scope.

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II. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Our application's operating principle is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Proposed System

A. Authentication

Here is our Login and Logout Page In which by entering our details we can sign up once then log in with the username and password and we can even log out from the given option as shown in fig 2.

B. Algorithm

The application was created with Android Studio and

numerous APIs and libraries that were embedded in the code. The following is a detailed explanation:

1) Taking the photograph: Image Picker 2.1 library is used to capture the image. As shown in Fig. 3, the user has two options for submitting the image for detection.

- Live image capture utilizing the device's camera
- Direct from the gallery

2) Image Processing: The selected image is processed as

As shown in Fig. 4, image cropping libraries are used to crop the image and focus on crucial information such as the name of the medicine.

'com.theartofdev.edmodo:android-image-cropper:2.8.+' is the library used.

The library's most important features are:

- Crop Image Activity is pre-installed.
- Choose Bitmap, Resource, or Android URI as the cropping image (Gallery, Camera, Dropbox, etc.).
- Rotation/flipping of images during cropping.
- Zoom in/out to the relevant cropping area automatically.

- f) In pixels, set the generated image's min/max bounds.
- g) Determine the size and position of the initial crop window.
- h) Ask for a cropped image to be resized to a certain size.

Image to Text: The text encoded in the image is recognized using the Google vision library.

The library used is 'com.google.android.gms:play-services-mlkit-text-recognition:18.0.0'

Key features of the library are

- a) Designed with dense text and documents in mind.
- b) Extracts information about a page, a block, a paragraph, a word, and a break.
- c) For each Text Block, Line, and Element object, you can get the text recognized in the region and the bounding coordinates of the region.

C. Output:

The text extracted from the image is now saved as a string, which we can obtain using Google's image to text library. The medical database has been created in.txt format. Now, using the string. Contains () method, each word in the string of required drug is compared to the database accessible. [6] If the medicine's name matches the database, we receive the result shown in Fig. 6.

The result is as follows:

- Name
- Use
- Patient Review
- Side Effects
- Price
- Dosage

III. LIMITATIONS

- 1) OCR's efficiency varies depending on the algorithm; therefore, we may not always get the results we want.
- 2) The size of a word's font significantly impacts its relevance. We can recognize it as humans, but OCR cannot.
- 3) The result will not be displayed if the scanned drug is not in the database.
- 4) Internet Connection is mandatory for login.
- 5) To search medicine in the database, our application needs precise cropping of a name.

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

- 1) OCR's efficiency varies depending on the algorithm; therefore, we may not always get the results we want.
- 2) We can include a chatbot to help with any issues that arise.
- 3) We can more databases through APIS directly.
- 4) Using web scraping to automatically display the appropriate result when searching for medication information.
- 5) We can decrease the intervened time between the search for medicine and make it to search within a second.

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